

ISic1387

Fragmentary Greek inscription (funerary?)

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary (?)

Material

stone

Object

unknown

Editor

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Principal Contributor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-06-14 - Jonathan Prag edited the file in line with edition prepared for Adrano museum catalogue

Place of origin (ancient)

Adranon

Place of origin (modern)

Adrano

Provenance

Reported at second-hand by Torremuzza (1769), who was sent the text by Nicolaus Capretti.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Neither the material nor the form of this inscription is recorded.

Dimensions

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Since the text is only recorded in the second-hand transcription by Torremuzza, nothing reliable can be said about the letter-forms.

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. Ἀρχε[---]

2. [---]ας

3. Πολυσ[---]

Apparatus

Text derived from Torremuzza 1769

Torremuzza gives no indication that anything is missing after the sigma

Translation

Commentary

The stone is probably a funerary inscription. Franz (CIG [<https://>

www.zotero.org/groups/382445/items/HTUDQBX5] III, 5737) proposed expanding the text as Ἀρχε[λαΐδ]ας Πολυσ[τράτου] or Πολυσ[θένους] (i.e. “(tombstone) of Archelaidas, son of Polystratos/Polysthenes”). However, the name Ἀρχελαΐδας [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?name=%E1%BC%88%CF%81%CF%87%CE%B5%CE%BB%CE%B1%CE%90%CE%B4%CE%B1%CF%82] is not attested for Sicily, and the alternatives in Ἀρχε- known for the island mostly do not end in -ας (Ἀρχέδαμος is common; Ἀρχεθάλης, Ἀρχέλας, Ἀρχέστρατος, Ἀρχέτιμος, Ἀρχέτιος are all found). Πολύστρατος [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?name=%CE%A0%CE%BF%CE%BB%CF%8D%CF%83%CF%84%CF%81%CE%B1%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%82] is attested once on Sicily, Πολυσθένης [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?name=%CE%A0%CE%BF%CE%BB%CF%85%CF%83%CE%B8%CE%AD%CE%BD%CE%B7%CF%82] is rare and not known in western Greece/Sicily. Torremuzza does not indicate anything was missing after the final letter, and the rare name Πόλυς [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?name=%CE%A0%CF%8C%CE%BB%CF%85%CF%82] is attested in Sicily, on a vase inscription from Gela of the fifth century BC (Dubois, IGDS 142 c; = Arena, Iscr. Sic. II 23), although one would then expect Πολυος for the genitive patronymic.

It is impossible to date this text, in the absence of further information, although it is most likely to belong to the Hellenistic period.

Digital identifiers:

TM 493002

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Bibliography

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At 59-60

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